

What about the Usability in Low-Code Platforms? A Systematic Literature Review

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Planning

Discover more about low-code and no-code tools and their relationship with usability, its quality, most relevant factors, and users' views on low-code and no-code tools

PICOC

- **Population:** Researchers, practitioners, low-code platform developers and users
- **Intervention:** Low-code tools, no-code tools
- **Comparison:** n/a
- **Outcome:** Concerns about usability and UX in low-code and no-code tools
- **Context:** Research and practice on low-code and no-code

Research Questions

1. What is the notion of the low-code concept among researchers and practitioners?
2. Do practitioners and researchers consider the usability of LCD tools?
3. What are the usability discussion points most commonly identified?
4. Which benefits and pitfalls of LCD tools are most common?

Search String

("low-code" or "no-code") AND ("user experience" OR "UX" OR "usability")

Sources

- ACM Digital Library (<http://portal.acm.org>)
- IEEE Digital Library (<http://ieeexplore.ieee.org>)
- Science@Direct (<http://www.sciencedirect.com>)
- Scopus (<http://www.scopus.com>)
- Springer Link (<http://link.springer.com>)

Selection Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- article deals with low-code or no-code
- document is a single work (article, paper, or book chapter)
- full-text is available electronically

Exclusion Criteria:

- paper does not use references
- paper is a secondary or tertiary study
- paper has low quality
- paper is not written in English

Data Extraction Form

- Authors' countries
- Authors' institutions
- Year
- Type of publication
- Title of publication
- Name of venue
- Main contribution
- Experimental evaluation
- Research approach
- Notion of LCD/NCD
- Benefits of LCD/NCD
- Pitfalls of LCD/NCD
- Usability of LCD/NCD

Conducting

Digital Libraries Search Strings

Imported Studies

- **ACM Digital Library:** 48
- **IEEE Digital Library:** 4
- **Science@Direct:** 119
- **Scopus:** 23
- **Springer Link:** 13